

Interview Protocol

[Introduction]

Thank you for agreeing to participate in this interview. Today's session focuses on your interaction with **PM-Sampo**, a web-based application designed to support a structured approach to analysing **provenance data** published as **Linked Data**. By integrating object metadata with historical events, places, and actors—and enabling this data to be explored through rich visualizations—PM-Sampo aims to help heritage researchers and practitioners conduct large-scale provenance analysis.

Currently, PM-Sampo is populated with 26,180 objects metadata from the **Wereldmuseum**, which has been documented as having connection with historical events and have been published as Linked Data via the **Colonial Collections Data Hub**. Through this portal, users can explore complex connections that might otherwise remain hidden—such as overlapping timelines of collection, networks of collectors, or patterns in object origins and acquisition.

This interview aims to understand how users like yourself engage with PM-Sampo for **knowledge discovery**, particularly in identifying **unexpected or serendipitous insights** in heritage object provenance research. We're interested in both the opportunities and the limitations that you encounter while using PM-Sampo for exploratory knowledge discovery.

Structure of the Interview

The interview will take approximately **1 hour** and is divided into **three phases**:

- 1. Pre-Interview: Demographic Questionnaire:** You will be asked to fill out a short questionnaire focused on your professional background in provenance research. Please note that no sensitive personal information such as your name or age will be requested.
- 2. Interview: Tool Exploration:** In this phase, you will explore the PM-Sampo web application through a combination of guided video demonstrations and hands-on tasks. First, a short video will introduce you to the tool and its basic features. Then, you will then explore the tool yourself and complete a task, with support from the interviewer as needed. After that, a second video will walk you through additional features of PM-Sampo. Following that, you will again explore the tool and complete a follow-up task based on the new features.
- 3. Post-Interview: Experience Survey (5 minutes):** You will complete a short survey to share your feedback and reflections on using the tool, including the usefulness and unexpectedness of your findings, and your overall experience.

Consent and Audio & Screen Recording

[Give the participant the consent form]

You've already had the opportunity to review the consent form, which outlines your rights and how your participation and data will be handled as part of this study.

Just to reinstate before we begin:

- **If yes:** Thank you! If at any time you would like me to pause or stop the recording—or if there is something you'd like to say off the record—please let me know.
- **If no:** No problem at all. I will take detailed notes during the interview. Please feel free to speak openly, and let me know if you'd like clarification on anything as we proceed.

Before we begin, do you have any questions about the study or today's session?

[Pause for questions]

If you think of any questions later—either during or after the interview—please don't hesitate to reach out. I'd be happy to clarify anything related to this research or your participation.

Demographic Information (Pre-Interview)

Before we begin the interview, I'd like to ask you a few brief background questions. These are just to help us better understand your professional context and experience in relation to provenance research and your interaction with museum collections, such as those from the Wereldmuseum. This will only take a few minutes, and your responses will remain confidential and used solely for research purposes.

[Give the participant the demographic Information form]

In the meantime, I will start recording and set-up the screen...

[Start the audio and screen recordings]

[Ask the participant to join zoom or team call – microphone and sound in mute]

Structure of the Interview

The interview will take approximately 50 minutes, and will be divided into three parts:

1. Introduction and Walkthrough Video (20 minutes)
2. Interactive Exploration (20 minutes)
3. Survey Questionnaire (10 minutes)

We are going to do it in two parts using two different perspectives: objects and actors.

Perspective: Collections

1. Introduction & Walkthrough Video (15 minutes)

We'll begin with a short guided walkthrough of PM-Sampo "Objects" perspective. Through a video, I'll explain the type of data available in the system, demonstrate its key features incorporated to facilitate object metadata exploration, and briefly showcase how you can explore information about object collection, object provenance, acquisition timelines, and connection with historical events.

2. Interactive Exploration (10 minutes)

You will then have time to explore PM-Sampo on your own. During this phase, you will perform the following tasks.

Task-1: Start with a filter that interests you and list down 5 finding that you came up through the tool and list them down, it could be both previously known or new.

- Look for patterns, for example, major object collectors, frequent places of origin, or key actors and their connections, active time-periods for object acquisition given different filters or gaps in the records.
- Follow your own research questions or curiosities, especially using the newly introduced features.

[Start the video: demonstrate perspective: "Objects"]

[Repeat Task-1 and ask the participant to do the Task-1]

This part of the interview follows a "Think-Aloud" protocol—please feel free to verbalise your thoughts, reactions, and questions as you navigate the interface. I will be here to assist if you need help with the tool or encounter any issues.

[Give the participant the list of Finding form → perspective: "Objects"]

[Unshare your screen and put the microphone in mute]

[Ask the participant to share their screen and microphone unmute]

Perspective: Actors

1. Introduction & Walkthrough (5 minutes)

Again, we'll begin with a short guided walkthrough video of PM-Sampo. Here, I'll explain who is considered as an actor in the system, demonstrate key features added for the actor, which is actor-actor relations, and briefly showcase how you can explore information about actors, their collections, actor's overall acquisition date, actor's biography and connection with other actor's or historical events.

2. Interactive Exploration (10 minutes)

You will then have time to explore PM-Sampo on your own. During this phase, you will perform the following tasks.

Task-2: Start with an actor that interests you and list down 5 finding that you came up through the tool and list them down; it could be both previously known or new.

- Look for patterns, for example, actor's connection with other actors, actor's connection with historical events, does actors collection pattern overlaps with known historical events, actor's active time-periods for object acquisition or gaps in the records.
- Follow your own research questions or curiosities, especially using the newly introduced features.

[Start the video: demonstrate perspective: "Actors"]

[Repeat Task-2 and ask the participant to do the Task-2]

This part of the interview follows a "Think-Aloud" protocol—please feel free to verbalise your thoughts, reactions, and questions as you navigate the interface. I will be here to assist if you need help with the tool or encounter any issues.

[Give the participant the list of Finding form → perspective: "Actors"]

[Unshare your screen and put the microphone in mute]

[Ask the participant to share their screen and microphone unmute]

3. Survey Questionnaire (5 minutes)

In the final part, you will be asked to fill out a brief survey that captures your experience using PM-Sampo. This includes looking back at the findings you listed earlier and evaluating them using a 5-point Likert Scale, reflecting concepts such as usefulness and unexpectedness. These insights are essential to help us understand the value of knowledge discovery within Linked Data-based research environments. At the end, through the tool evaluation form you will reflect about your overall experience with PM-Sampo.

[Give the participant Interestingness Assessment form and tool evaluation form]

Demographic Information (Pre-Interview Questions)

Please provide the following background information. Your responses will help us better understand your professional context and experience relevant to this study.

1. Current Professional Role

(e.g., Researcher, Curator, Archivist, PhD Student, etc.)

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2. Affiliated Institution

(e.g., University, Museum, Archive, Research Center)

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3. Years of Experience in Provenance Research

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4. Years of Experience Working with Wereldmuseum Collections

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5. Information Systems, Tools, or Websites You Regularly Use for Your Research

(e.g., TMS, Nationaal Archief, Colonial Collections, other museum databases or portals)

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List of 5 Interesting Findings (*facts, patterns or connections*):

Perspective: Objects

Finding-1

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Finding-2

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Finding-3

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Finding-4

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Finding-5

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List of 5 Interesting Findings (*facts, patterns or connections*):

Perspective: Actors

Finding-6

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Finding-7

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Finding-8

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Finding-9

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Finding-10

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Interestingness Assessment Scale

In this section, we would like you to reflect on the findings you listed earlier (Findings 1–10). For each item, you will evaluate your experience along two subjective dimensions of **interestingness**:

1. **Actionability** – *To what extent did you find the findings useful for provenance researchers?*
2. **Unexpectedness** – *To what extent was the item surprising or something you did not anticipate?*

Now, refer to the findings you listed earlier (Finding-1, Finding-2, and so on).

For each of these findings, we provide **two statements**—one about how *useful* the finding is, and another about how *unexpected* it is.

Please review each statement carefully and indicate your level of agreement using the scale provided.

You may use the following agreement scale for each statement:

- **- 2 = Strongly Disagree**
- **- 1 = Disagree**
- **0 = Neither Agree Nor Disagree**
- **1 = Agree**
- **2 = Strongly Agree**

If you feel a particular item does not fit the criteria, you may leave that row blank.

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neither Agree Nor Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
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Finding-1

The finding was useful	<input type="checkbox"/>				
The finding was surprising or unexpected	<input type="checkbox"/>				

Finding-2

The finding was useful	<input type="checkbox"/>				
The finding was surprising or unexpected	<input type="checkbox"/>				

Finding-3

The finding was useful	<input type="checkbox"/>				
The finding was surprising or unexpected	<input type="checkbox"/>				

Finding-4

The finding was useful	<input type="checkbox"/>				
The finding was surprising or unexpected	<input type="checkbox"/>				

Finding-5

The finding was useful	<input type="checkbox"/>				
The finding was surprising or unexpected	<input type="checkbox"/>				

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neither Agree Nor Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
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Finding-6

The finding was **useful**

The finding was **surprising or unexpected**

Finding-7

The finding was **useful**

The finding was **surprising or unexpected**

Finding-8

The finding was **useful**

The finding was **surprising or unexpected**

Finding-9

The finding was **useful**

The finding was **surprising or unexpected**

Finding-10

The finding was **useful**

The finding was **surprising or unexpected**

Tool Evaluation: PM-Sampo for Knowledge Discovery

Please indicate how much you agree or disagree with the following statements about PM-Sampo as a tool for discovering new knowledge and supporting your research.

Statement	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
1. I would consider using PM-Sampo in my own research for exploring heritage object provenance.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
2. I think PM-Sampo has potential to uncover relationships or insights I might not have discovered otherwise.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
3. I plan to use PM-Sampo in my future research to support knowledge discovery.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
4. PM-Sampo enables exploratory analysis that aligns with my research interests.	<input type="checkbox"/>				

Please take a moment to answer the following questions

1. *Write down three aspects/features of PM-Sampo that you find most useful for your work or research interests?*

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2. *Do you have any other comments, suggestions, or reflections about your experience?*

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Stay Connected? (Optional)

Would you like to stay informed about the outcomes of this research and future updates?

- Yes; please provide your email address below.
- No

Reminder: Your email address will be stored and used for communication related to this research project.

Email address: _____